

PREPARING FUTURE PRIMARY CLASS TEACHERS FOR PROFESSIONAL ACTIVITY BASED ON THE DEVELOPMENT OF THEIR DIGITAL COMPETENCIES

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Abstract. *The results of the assessment of the digital competence of the future elementary school teachers presented in the study are used for planning the modernization of the content of educational subjects related to the use of information and communication technologies in teaching, developing continuous education and training programs. is of practical importance in output.*

Keywords: *future primary school teachers, digital competence, information and communication technologies, continuous education.*

The constant growth of the amount of information and the limitation of the time of the educational process imposes the need to intensify teaching, develop and use non-traditional technologies based on the use of computing techniques with the use of active teaching methods. The implementation of active methods is one of the main tasks of didactics, it implies the activation of the entire process, the identification of systems and methods that allow to increase the activity of future elementary school teachers by forming a positive motivational structure of educational activities.

The changing informational and cultural environment puts a number of complex tasks before modern pedagogy, which are new for society. The development of new modern information and communication technologies has changed the information environment in which human development and social work are carried out. Modern media, in many cases, have become carriers of social norms, values and rules that people adhere to. At the same time, new information technologies have become an amplifier of human intelligence, storing, processing and producing information at a new level. Information literacy and media competence have become one of the important qualities of a modern person, which allows 2].

While preserving the most important achievements of humanity, the new information culture requires the development of new intellectual activity that allows him to perform his activities more efficiently in the information world.

Today, the digitization of the higher education system implies the widespread introduction of digital technologies in all areas of the educational institution, and the future primary school teachers requires the formation and assessment of appropriate professional training, their digital competence. Focuses on developing the digital literacy of future primary school teachers. The integration of digital technologies into the educational process is important because it is aimed at developing pedagogical methods and approaches, opening new opportunities in terms of personalization of the educational process. The digital competences of the future primary school teachers are considered in the modern scientific heritage as a result of the evolutionary development of their digital competences, which is declared in the teacher's professional standard as an indispensable characteristic of a teacher in modern conditions. This is the basis for the

development of digital literacy of future elementary school teachers of higher education institutions. The teacher should play an important role in adapting digital innovations to improve the quality of learning.

The tendency of higher education to create a high-tech digital educational environment predetermines the important role of the teacher who "fills this environment, determines its nature in action, adapts new tools to achieve didactic goals." In this case, the determining principle is the teacher's digital competence. Many studies on the digital competence **Ошибка! Источник ссылки не найден.** already been carried out, including AAAbdugadirov[**Ошибка! Источник ссылки не найден.**], REF_Ref93393066 \r \h * MERGEFORMAT RXDjuraev **Ошибка! Источник ссылки не найден.**], L.Ilomaki[**Ошибка! Источник ссылки не найден.**], G.Faloon[**Ошибка! Источник ссылки не найден.**], BRMandel[**Ошибка! Источник ссылки не найден.**], at the international level REF_Ref52055036 \r \h * MERGEFORMAT, the main features of the manifestation of digital competence are revealed. Digital competence is still mentioned as a new important component of the teacher's competence category, but the methodology of its assessment has not yet been developed in detail in practice.

The purpose of this study is to analyze the current state of digital competence of future primary school teachers based on the analysis of empirical data obtained during a survey on the use of digital technologies in the educational process of future primary school teachers. determined to be determined. In the conditions of digitization of the educational environment of higher education, teachers should solve the following number of tasks in the process of learning their digital competence. These analyzes describe the manifestation of digital competencies. Conducting a survey to determine the digital competence of future primary school teachers, form conclusions about the current state of digital competence of future primary school teachers, future primary school determines the prospects of research in the field of digital competence of teachers.

We believe that the system of professional training and digital competence of future elementary school teachers can be effective only if the following organizational and pedagogical conditions are provided. These include the following.

Organizational conditions: development of educational programs, taking into account the trends in the development of modern information and communication technologies in the training of future primary school teachers;

– to create a new information and educational environment for training pedagogues who have the skills to effectively use modern information and communication technologies in the future;

– providing students with the opportunity to create a personal electronic environment to individualize their professional training as future elementary school teachers; Electronic environment means information systems (Hemis, Moodle), e-mail, chat, chat-forum, ISQ, IP-telephony, blogs, video blog, live journals, Wikipedia, interactive media technology, online video conference systems;

– providing a high-quality material and technical base of training for professional activity;

– extensive use of modern information and communication technologies in the educational process;

– building strong relationships with employers;

– organizing and conducting pedagogical and production practices focused on the use of modern pedagogical and information technologies.

Pedagogical conditions: development of methodological approaches and didactic principles in the process of formation of professional skills of future primary school teachers ;

- theoretical and practical training of the teacher in information and communication technologies for the formation and development of digital competence;

- organization of a digital learning environment;

- improvement of the curriculum and programs based on the credit-module system of teaching.

- development and continuous updating of educational materials and information resources for e-learning;

- individualization of education, creating conditions for determining the personal educational trajectory of future elementary school teachers

- establishing mutual cooperation relations with industry and employers;

- development of a motivational system for in-depth study of the field of science;

- to determine the competence groups included in the professional competences of future elementary school teachers and to carry out continuous monitoring;

- choosing the content of professional training of future primary school teachers ;

- development and constant updating of educational materials and information resources for quality training of future primary school teachers ;

- use appropriate forms, methods, tools, methodical approaches and teaching technologies to form the digital competence of future elementary school teachers ;

- involvement in self-management, self-learning and self-development in future elementary school teachers ;

Based on the above, as well as the theoretical analysis of the studied literature, it is possible to determine the digital competence of future elementary school teachers as a set of certain personal and communicative qualities and communicative skills.

Research methodology was carried out to study the digital competence of future primary school teachers. Today, most of the future elementary teachers and most of the teachers are already working with digital technologies, while the other part is just getting acquainted and gaining experience. Various digital tools and services that can be useful for future elementary teachers were considered in the study of "Technologies for the creation of e-learning resources". This subject "Vocational education in the field of information and communication technologies" is taught in the 3rd year, 5th semester. The long-term practice of working with future elementary school teachers shows that many people are interested in the content of this subject program, which is required for practical training in new, higher educational institutions. In most cases, according to the results of a survey of trainees and students, prospective elementary teachers use only a part of the digital tools and services offered [**Ошибка! Источник ссылки не найден.**].

Based on this, it is necessary to develop and practice methods for evaluating the digital competence of future elementary school teachers.

It is planned to reveal general information about the description, familiarization of future elementary school teachers with the assessment of the culture of working with digital tools and services. Future elementary teachers need to learn how to interact using digital technologies, what digital tools and services are used to develop digital content; how digital technologies are used; it is necessary to determine the extent to which prospective elementary teachers are ready to flexibly integrate online learning elements into the educational environment.

Digital technologies play a key role in organizing the educational process. They can be used as an educational tool for organizing active cognitive activity, cooperation. Today, the digital competences of the teacher have a universal character and provide the participants of the educational process with mechanisms to adapt to the digitization of society, and the digital competence of the teacher is the basis for the full participation of teachers and students in the educational environment, the desire of students "serves to reveal tastes[**Ошибка! Источник ссылки не найден.**].

In the conditions of digitization of higher education, the current direction of development of modern pedagogical research is to create a fundamental scientific base of the process of training teachers and improve their qualifications for working in a digital educational environment.

The necessity of forming the teacher's digital competence and the relevance of developing methods for its evaluation were noted.

The teacher is considered as the central object of higher education in the environment of digital technology, he is not only responsible for the transfer of science knowledge, solving the problems of teaching, learning and development, but also performing new functions, the future primary class. is a trainer of teachers and is responsible for their formation. Moreover, it is precisely such a teacher who will have to make profound changes in order to improve his quality. At the same time, it includes the interactivity of the educational process, the maximum involvement of future elementary school teachers in joint activities, the form of cross-platform communicative interaction, the individualization of educational trajectories, etc. takes

Academician Gusolatova conducted research on digital competence and the research results were presented in her scientific works. However, with the rapid development of digital technologies and their increasing role in education, digital competence can be considered a starting point. The scope of the concept is proportionally determined by the dynamics of the development of digital technologies. At the same time, scholars include knowledge, skills, motivation and responsibility in the composition of digital competence, which is carried out in four directions (content, communication, consumption and technosphere). In this regard, in our study, the digital competence of future elementary school teachers is the ability of the teacher to choose and use information and communication technologies and digital technologies reliably, effectively, critically and safely in various areas of life based on continuous learning. considered as Digital Competencies:

- 1) work with content (creation, search, selection, critical evaluation of content);
- 2) communication (creating, developing, maintaining relationships, identity, reputation, self-expression);
- 3) consumption (using the Internet for consumer purposes - orders, services, purchases, etc.);
- 4) technosphere (computer and software skills), as well as the teacher's readiness for such activities. Taking into account the groups of information and communication technologies competencies in the terminology of UNESCO, it is recommended to talk about their development in the classroom of the teacher's general user, general pedagogical and science-pedagogical digital competencies. Digital competences are described on the basis of the European model of digital competences for education, while the digital competence of teachers is not assessed. At the same time, it is necessary to determine the current landscape of digital competence of teachers, to assess their readiness to work in modern information and communication technologies and the desire of

teachers to use digital technologies in the educational process after the mandatory rapid development of digital tools and services, as well as during the pandemic innovations are widely implemented [**Ошибка! Источник ссылки не найден.**].

Future elementary school teachers should use the services of working with electronic educational content in the conditions of modern information, telecommunication and technological infrastructure of higher education institutions, master electronic (online) professional development programs. Conducting classes using e-learning content, as well as laboratory and practical work using interactive e-learning materials, including virtual laboratories, simulators, etc. All this implies updating the didactic digital tools of the teacher, designing the environment of electronic educational technologies.

Practice of digital technologies. The services regularly used by the teacher to ensure the educational process and carry out pedagogical activities from a personal device include: services for working with electronic educational content, electronic journal, electronic spreadsheet, taking into account the development of additional educational programs acquisition, information and communication educational platform, electronic reporting services, etc.

Because digital services, tools, and environments are so dynamic, they are constantly evolving and improving. In this regard, the constant updating and development of digital competences, the formation of the digital competence of the teacher is important for the convenient, effective and safe use of digital competences in pedagogical activities [60 **Ошибка! Источник ссылки не найден.**].

The digital competence of the future elementary school teachers in our study is determined by general user, general pedagogical and scientific-educational digital competences and three levels of its progressive development (main purpose, digital use, digital transformation), its cognitive, functional and creative aspects (Figure 2.1).

Figure 2.1. Three levels of digital competence development.

Based on the indicated levels of digital competence of future primary school teachers, we investigated the current situation and determined the general readiness of future primary school teachers to use digital technologies in their work. In the future, this will allow us to talk about the means of forming the digital competence of future elementary school teachers.

The quality of open educational materials, their fragmentation, lack of ability to integrate resources and tools from different platforms. The results of the study of digital competence allow

predicting the pedagogical means of its formation. At the same time, we believe that digital competence is simultaneously: 1) an educational result of professional training of future elementary school teachers; 2) the result of self-development of future elementary school teachers; 3) the result of synthesizing the pedagogical (activity and personal) experience of future elementary school teachers.

In this regard, pedagogical tools for the formation of digital competence can be presented in three thematic blocks:

1) modeling the trajectory of personal education of future elementary school teachers during the period of studying at an educational institution, undergoing pedagogical practice, and taking advanced training courses: use of e-learning resources in the educational process, as well as digital platforms for education (including ready-made high-quality e-learning content), organization of joint projects in the online environment, interaction in cloud services and pedagogical communication; development of network activity and communication in social networks; use of digital tools and services in the design of various educational lesson situations, creation of electronic educational content.

This allows to form the readiness of the teacher to work in modern information and communication technologies, to show possible options for working in new conditions, to encourage the use of digital technologies in the educational process, to conduct propaedeutic work on the formation of initial personal experience[**Ошибка! Источник ссылки не найден.**].

2) improving the skills of future elementary school teachers on the implementation of the digitized educational process, developing methodological training in the direction of digital transformation of education using modern online educational platforms, web- a natural practice-oriented environment for the formation of digital competencies of future elementary school teachers to participate in seminars and others;

3) exchange of positive and negative pedagogical experiences within network pedagogical communities; participation in creative contests within priority national projects on digitalization of education, study of local and foreign pedagogical experience. It creates a complete picture of the advantages and disadvantages of using digital technologies in the educational process, determines the level of their effective implementation in practice.

Thus, we can conclude that digital competence is an important professional characteristic of a teacher of higher education institutions in the environment of digital technologies. In connection with the rapid development of digital technologies, their increasing role in human life and activities, the issues of determining its essence, level, and methods of evaluation are becoming urgent.

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